

INFLATION AND UNEMPLOYMENT NEXUS IN NIGERIA: A TEST OF VALIDATION OF THE PHILLIPS CURVE

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Abstract

Empirical analysis of the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria has produced divergent results. This study investigated the inflation-unemployment nexus in Nigeria as a test of validation of the Phillips curve hypothesis. Per capita real gross domestic product, gross fixed capital formation, and total government expenditure were introduced as control variables. Annual time-series data from 1981 to 2023 were analysed using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, Johansen cointegration test and error correction mechanism (ECM). The findings revealed that inflation rate has insignificant positive impact on unemployment rate. On the other hand, per capita real gross domestic product and gross fixed capital formation have significant negative impact on unemployment rate while total government expenditure has insignificant negative impact on unemployment rate. The study concludes that the Phillips curve does not exist in Nigeria. Rather, what exists in Nigeria is stagflation. Among other things, it is recommended that supply-side economic policies that will boost economic productivity, reduce costs of production, stabilize prices, and create a conducive macroeconomic environment for sustainable economic growth and job creation should be implemented.

Introduction

The relationship between inflation and unemployment has often been described as an inverse relationship, implying that when one increases, the other decreases. Thus, inflation and unemployment have historically maintained an inverse relationship, as represented by the Phillips curve. Hence, low levels of inflation typically corresponded with higher unemployment rates, while high rates of inflation corresponded with low

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unemployment rates (Palley, 2011; Alisa, 2015). The explanation for this inverse relationship is that low unemployment (i.e., when more people are working) means more people have the discretionary income to purchase goods and services. This brings about an increase in the demand for goods and services. Workers can also bargain for higher wages, which are transmitted to consumers in the form of higher prices. But when unemployment is high, consumers purchase fewer goods and services due to deficiency in income. This puts downward pressure on prices bringing about a reduction in the rate of inflation (Alisa, 2015; Negro et al, 2020). Inflation and unemployment remain burning issues especially among developing countries. Every economy would, to a large extent, wish to achieve low rates of inflation and unemployment without recession. It is often asserted that a single-digit inflation rate and an unemployment rate of about five percent would ensure macroeconomic stability in an economy (Gyang et al, 2018). Nigeria is facing significant challenges with both inflation and unemployment, which are interconnected issues impacting the country's macroeconomic stability and citizens' well-being negatively. Nigeria's inflation rate has persistently exceeded the central bank's 6-9 percent target range, covering about 20 percent in recent years. Nigeria's unemployment rate has equally surged, reaching 33.3 percent in 2023 with youth unemployment at an alarming 42.5 percent (Egole, 2023; Musa et al, 2024).

Meanwhile, the Phillips curve postulates an inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment. This implies that a trade-off exists between the two phenomena. The implication is that policies targeted at reducing inflation may end up aggravating unemployment and vice versa. However, from available statistics, both inflation and unemployment have been increasing in Nigeria. This presupposes that the expected trade-off between the two phenomena, postulated by the Phillips curve, is not the case with Nigeria. In fact, what seems to operate in Nigeria is referred to as stagflation-the coexistence of high rate of inflation with high unemployment rate. Nigeria has therefore found itself entangled in a challenging combination of soaring inflation, economic downturn, and mounting joblessness. Infact, data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) show that Nigeria's inflation rate increased from 28.92 percent in December, 2023 to 29.9 percent in January, 2024. Similarly, the unemployment rate increased from 4.2 percent to 5.0 percent in the third quarter of 2024. Thus, the simultaneous increases in both macroeconomic indicators-unemployment and inflation rates-amidst sluggish GDP growth rate define stagflation, underscoring a troubling economic scenario. The implication is that the conventional monetary and fiscal policy measures designed to combat inflation and unemployment may likely not achieve significant success in a country like Nigeria experiencing stagflation (Tombofa & Anaele, 2002; Okwesili, 2024; Ojabello, 2024).

The foregoing discussion shows that Nigeria seems to be experiencing stagflation instead of the expected trade-off between inflation and unemployment as postulated by the Phillips Curve. However, empirical analysis of the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria has produced divergent results. Hence, there is no clear-cut empirical evidence to show that the Phillips curve exists in Nigeria or not. It is therefore necessary to confront the phenomenon with recent empirical data. This study therefore examined the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria so as to test the validity or otherwise of the Phillips curve.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.1 Inflation

Inflation refers to a sustained upward trend in the general level of prices and not just the prices of only one or few goods. It is the persistent, sustained and appreciable rise in the general level of prices of goods and services (Ahuja, 2013). The inflation rate is a measure of the rate at which the consumer price index (CPI) changes over a specified period of time. It is a quantitative measure of the rate at which the average price level of a basket of

selected goods and services in the economy increases over a period of time. It is the rise in the general level of prices where a unit of currency effectively buys less than it did in prior periods. Thus, the inflation rate indicates a decrease in the purchasing power of a country's currency (Anyanwucha, 2006). The inflation rate is measured in percentage, and for this study, the annual inflation rate is used.

2.1.2 Unemployment

The unemployed refers to individuals who are employable (i.e., those who are able to work) and seeking for a job at the prevailing wage rate, but are unable to find one (Ohale & Onyema, 2002). Therefore, unemployment is defined as the number of persons within the working age bracket who are willing and able to work at the prevailing wage rate, but cannot find a job.

The unemployment rate refers to the number of persons considered unemployed, expressed a percentage of the total labour force. That is, Unemployment Rate

$$= \frac{\text{Number of Unemployed Persons} \times 100}{\text{Labour}}$$

2.2 Theoretical Literature review

The Phillips Curve

A notable British economist, A.W. Phillips, published an article in 1958 based on his good deal of research using historical data from the United Kingdom for about 100 years in which he arrived at the conclusion that “there infact existed an inverse relationship between rate of unemployment and rate of inflation”. This inverse relationship implies a trade-off, that is, for reducing unemployment, price in the form of a higher rate of inflation has to be paid, and for reducing the rate of inflation, price in terms of a higher rate of unemployment has to be borne. On graphically fitting a curve to the historical data, Phillips obtained a downward slopping curve exhibiting the inverse relationship between the rate of inflation and the rate of unemployment. This curve is now named after him as “Phillips Curve” (Ahuja, 2013).

The actual Phillips curve drawn from the data of the 1960s (1961-1969) for the United States also depicts the inverse relationship between unemployment rate and the rate of inflation. Similarly, empirical data pertaining to the 1950s and 1960s for other developed countries seemed to confirmed the Phillips curve hypothesis. On the basis of this, many economists came to believe that there existed a stable Phillips curve which depicted a predictable inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment. They further emphasized the trade-off that confronts economic policy makers on the basis of a stable Phillips curve for a country. This trade-off presents a dilemma for the policy makers (Dierks, 2023; Wang, 2023). Thus, during the 1960s, Phillips curve became an important concept of macroeconomic analysis. The stable relationship described by it suggested that policy makers could have a lower rate of unemployment if they could bear with a higher rate of inflation. On the other hand, they could achieve a lower rate of inflation only if they were prepared to reconcile with a higher rate of unemployment (Barsky & Killian, 2000; Jhingan, 2016).

However, during the 1970s, a strange phenomenon was experienced in the United States and Britain where there existed a high rate of inflation alongside a high rate of unemployment. This was contrary to both the Philips curve hypothesis and the simple Keynesian model. This concurrent existence of both high rate of inflation and high unemployment rate (or low level of real national product) during the 1970s and early 1980s has been described as stagflation (Helliwell, 1988; Burda & Wyplosz, 1997; Ahuja, 2013). Thus, a stable Phillips curve could not hold good during the 1970s and 1980s, especially in the United States. Therefore, experience in the two decades (1971-1991), has prompted some economists to say that the stable Phillips curve has collapsed. During these two decades, there were periods when rates of both inflation and unemployment increased, which shows the absence of trade-off. Based on data from the United States, it appears that instead

of remaining stable, the Phillips curve shifted to the right in the 1970s and early 1980s and to the left during the late 1980s (Blanchard, 2000; Ahuja, 2013; Jhingan, 2016).

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Onwuemeka et al (2024) found that inflation has insignificant positive impact on unemployment in Nigeria. Alhabarneh et al (2024) established that unemployment has significant negative impact on inflation in Jordan. Janoras et al (2024) showed that unemployment has significant positive impact on inflation in the Philippines. Aliyu et al (2024) found that an insignificant negative relationship exists between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. Similarly, Nwikpo (2023) observed that unemployment has significant negative impact on inflation in Nigeria. Also, Okeowo (2023) established that unemployment has insignificant negative impact on inflation in Nigeria. Effiong et al (2022) examined the relationship between inflation and unemployment in a panel of 6 countries within the West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ) including Nigeria. Using time-series data, the findings showed significant positive relationship between inflation and unemployment. However, using cross-section data to check country-specific results, the findings indicated that unemployment has insignificant positive impact on inflation in Guinea, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone; significant positive impact on inflation in Ghana and Liberia; and an insignificant negative impact on inflation in Gambia.

Further, Okoebor et al (2022) established insignificant positive impact of inflation on unemployment in Nigeria. On their part, Daniel et al (2021) studied the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria and concluded that inflation has insignificant negative impact on unemployment. Nautwima and Asa (2021) established significant negative relationship between inflation and unemployment in Namibia. Anoke et al (2021) found that inflation has significant positive impact on unemployment in Nigeria. In a similar study, Umar et al (2021) showed that unemployment has significant positive impact on inflation. Qin (2020) confirms the existence of the Phillips curve in the United States economy for the period 1962:Q2 to 2019:Q4. Kormaz and Abdullazade (2020) established unidirectional causality from inflation to unemployment among 9 of Group 6 (G6) countries. Babatunde et al (2020) found that unemployment has significant negative relationship with inflation in Nigeria. On the contrary, Nzidee and Uzorka (2019) found out that unemployment has significant positive impact on inflation in Nigeria. Irewole (2019) established that unemployment has insignificant positive impact on inflation in Nigeria and Mexico. Odo et al (2017) observed that inflation have significant positive impact on unemployment in Nigeria. Orji et al (2015) found that unemployment has significant positive impact on inflation in Nigeria.

From the empirical literature reviewed, it is observed that there is no consensus in the findings of previous studies on the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. In other words, while some studies found positive relationship between inflation and unemployment, other studies found negative relationship between the two variables. For instance, Orji et al (2015), Odo et al (2017), Irewole (2019), Nzidee and Uzorka (2019), Umar et al (2021), Anoke et al (2021), Okoebor et al (2022), and Onwuemeka et al (2024) established positive relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. The implication of the positive relationship is that the Phillips curve hypothesis does not exist in Nigeria. Rather, what exists is stagflation- the simultaneous existence of high inflation and unemployment rates. On the contrary, Babatunde et al (2020), Daniel et al (2021), Okeowo (2023), Nwikpo (2023), and Aliyu et al (2024) found that there exists negative relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. The implication is that the Phillips curve hypothesis exists in Nigeria.

Based on the above gap identified in the literature on the relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria, there is the need to confront the phenomenon with recent empirical data to find out the actual

relationship between inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. This study therefore examined the relationship between unemployment and inflation in Nigeria, using annual time-series from 1981 to 2023.

3. METHOD OF STUDY

3.1 Model Specification

This study examined the relationship between unemployment and inflation in Nigeria. The model used for the study is specified based on the Phillips curve hypothesis and the analytical model used by Nwiko (2023) which is expressed in its functional form as follows:

$$INF = f (UMP, TGE, RGDP)----- (1)$$

where INF = Inflation Rate

TGE = Total Government Expenditure

RGDP = real Gross Domestic Product

The baseline model above was adopted with minor adjustment so as to allow for the inclusion of the variables of the present study. Therefore, the model for this study is expressed in its functional form as follows:

$$UNEMP= f (INFR, PCRDGP, GFCF, TGE)----- (2)$$

where UNEMP = Unemployment Rate

INFR = Inflation Rate

PCRDGP = Per Capita real Gross Domestic Product

GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation

TGE = Total Government Expenditure

f = Functionality Notation

UNEMP is the dependent variable while INFR is the independent variable. PCRDGP, GFCF, and TGE were introduced as control variables.

The econometric equation based on the functional form of the model is expressed as follows:

$$UNEMP =\beta_0+ \beta_1INFR +\beta_2PCRDGP + \beta_3GFCF+\beta_4TGE+U----- (3)$$

where β_0 is the regression intercept, $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ are the parameter estimates of the explanatory variables while U is the error term. All other variables are as earlier defined.

Equation (3) can be transformed into a logarithmic form as follows:

$$UNEMP =\beta_0+ \beta_1INFR +\beta_2LOGPCRDGP +\beta_3LOGGFCF+\beta_4LOGTGE+\varepsilon----- (4)$$

where LOG is the natural logarithm of the variables and ε is the log-transformed error term. All other variables are as earlier defined.

3.3.1 Apriori Theoretical Expectations

Based on economic theoretical reasoning, the followings signs of the parameter estimates are expected.

$$B_1 < 0, B_2 < 0, B_3 < 0, B_4 < 0$$

The implication of the above signs of the parameter estimates is that a negative relationship is expected between each of the explanatory variables and the dependent variable.

3.2 Description of Variables

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable for this study is unemployment rate. It is defined as the number of persons considered unemployed expressed as a percentage of the labour force in Nigeria in a year.

Explanatory Variables

- i. **Inflation Rate:** This is the percentage change in the consumer price index in Nigeria in a year.

- ii. **Per Capita Real Gross Domestic Product:** This is defined as the inflation-adjusted total monetary value of the final output of goods and services produced within Nigeria in a year divided by the total population of the country in a year. It is measured in millions of naira.
- iii. **Gross Fixed Capital Formation:** This is defined as resident producers' acquisition of produced assets, including purchases of second-hand assets and the production of such assets for own uses, minus disposal. It covers expenditure on capital goods such as machinery, equipment, buildings, etc. made within the geographical confines of Nigeria in a year. It is measured in billions of naira.
- iv. **Total Government Expenditure:** This is the total amount of money that the Federal Government of Nigeria spends in a year. It comprises both capital and recurrent expenditure. It is measured in billions of naira.

3.3 Nature and Sources of Data

The study made use of annual time-series data for the period 1981 to 2023. The data are secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual statistical bulletin for 2023, CBN reports and statements of accounts for various years, and the World Bank development indicators.

3.4 Techniques of Data Estimation

Considering the fact that the study made use of time-series data, there is the need to account for certain properties associated with such data. Specifically, there is the need to check whether the time-series variables are stationary or not, and to determine their various orders of integration. To this end, the data analytical procedure was started with stationarity test which was conducted using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. Based on the result of the ADF unit root test, the Johansen cointegration test was used to test the presence of long-run relationships among the variables of the study. Finally, the error correction mechanism (ECM) was used to test the short-run behaviour of the variables.

4. Presentation of Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The summary of the descriptive statistics result is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Result

	UNEMP	INFR	PCRGDP	GFCF	TGE
Mean	10.03744	18.85628	265.1628	8673.187	3186.495
Median	9.010000	13.25000	231.0000	8385.960	1018.200
Maximum	26.70000	72.80000	387.0000	15789.67	19808.40
Minimum	1.900000	5.400000	174.0000	4559.750	9.600000
Std. Dev.	6.238742	15.59680	75.79481	2085.202	4475.376
Skewness	0.721290	1.842818	0.329836	0.868583	1.925263
Kurtosis	2.743824	5.776650	1.380456	4.693890	6.601319
Jarque-Bera	3.846103	38.15122	5.479080	10.54756	49.80126
Probability	0.146160	0.000000	0.064600	0.005124	0.000000
Sum	431.6100	810.8200	11402.00	372947.1	137019.3
Sum Sq. Dev.	1634.720	10216.93	241283.9	1.83E+08	8.41E+08
Observations	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Computed from E-View

From the descriptive statistics result in table1, the variables have mean values of 10.03744 percent, 18.85628 percent, ₦265.1628 million, ₦8673.187 billion, ₦3186.495 billion for unemployment, inflation, per capita real GDP, gross fixed capital formation and total government expenditure respectively. Based on the standard

deviation statistic, total government expenditure with a standard deviation value of 4475.376 is the most unstable or most fluctuating variable while unemployment rate with a standard deviation value of 6.238742 is the most stable or least fluctuating variable. The skewness statistic indicated that all the variables are positively skewed. Based on the Kurtosis statistic, unemployment rate and per capita real GDP are platykurtic given that their values are less than 3. The implication is that they have lighter tails relative to normal distribution. On the other hand, inflation rate, gross fixed capital formation and total government expenditure are leptokurtic since their values are greater than 3. This means that they heavier tails relative to normal distribution.

4.2 Stationarity Test

The stationarity test was conducted using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: ADF Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF test Statistic (At levels)	Critical Values		Prob.	ADF test Statistic (at First Diff.)	Critical Values		Prob.	Order of Integration
		1%	5%			1%	5%		
UNEMP	-1.912300	-3.596616	-2.933158	0.3237	-7.100770*	-3.600987	-2.935001	0.0000	I(1)
INFR	-1.798694	-3.596616	-2.933158	0.0688	-6.101244*	-3.600987	-2.935001	0.0000	I(1)
PCRGDP	-2.297054	-3.605593	-2.936942	0.8021	-3.545736**	-3.600987	-2.935001	0.0115	I(1)
GFCF	-2.297054	-3.605593	-2.936942	0.1778	-5.572447*	-3.605593	-2.936942	0.0000	I(1)
TGE	2.826321	-3.596616	-2.933158	1.0000	-7.177996*	-3.605593	-2.936942	0.0000	I(1)

Source: Computed from E-view

Note: * and ** denote rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root at the one percent and 5 percent critical values respectively.

From ADF unit root test result in table 2, none of the variables are stationary at levels. However, they become stationary at first difference. UNEMP, INFR, GFCF and TGE become stationary at first difference at 5 percent critical value while PCRGDP become stationary at first difference at 1 percent critical value.

4.3 Cointegration Test

The result of the Johansen cointegration test are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Johansen Cointegration Test Result

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE_(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob**
None*	0.624538	99.74631	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1*	0.485282	60.56238	47.85613	0.0021
At most 2*	0.418620	33.99694	29.79707	0.0155
At most 3	0.243365	12.30294	15.49471	0.1430
At most 4	0.028291	1.147952	3.841466	0.2840
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized No. of CE_(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob**
None*	0.624538	39.18394	33.87687	0.0106
At most 1	0.485282	26.56544	27.58434	0.0671
At most 2	0.418620	21.69400	21.13162	0.0417
At most 3	0.243365	11.15498	14.26460	0.1466
At most 4	0.028291	1.147952	3.841466	0.2840

Source: Computed from E-View

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating 1 equations at the 0.05 level.

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating equation at the 0.05 level.

*denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

From the Johansen cointegration test result in table 3, the trace test indicated 3 cointegrating equations while the maximum eigenvalue test indicated one cointegrating equation. The result therefore shows the presence of long-run (equilibrium) relationships among the variables of the study.

4.3.1 Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients

The normalized cointegrating coefficients are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients

UNEMP	INFR	PCRGDP	GFCF	TGE
1.000000	-0.104295 (0.06293)	0.110474 (0.02301)	0.003606 (0.00073)	0.001416 (0.00085)

Source: Computed from E-view

Note: The figures in the brackets are the standard errors.

4.3.2 Estimated Long-Run Coefficient

The estimated long-run coefficients were obtained from the normalized cointegrating coefficients in table 4 after reversing the signs of the coefficients. The result is presented in table 5.

Table 5: Estimated Long-Run Coefficients

UNEMP	INFR	PCRGDP	GFCF	TGE
1.000000	0.104295 (0.06293) (1.657318)	-0.110474 (0.02301) (-4.801130)	-0.003606 (0.00073) (-4.939726)	-0.001416 (0.00085) (-1.665882)

Source: Computed from E-view

Note: The figures in the first and second brackets are the standard errors and the t-values respectively.

4.4 Optimal Lag Selection Test

The optimal lag order selection test result is presented in table 6. The optimal lag length is the one that minimizes the Akaike information criterion, Schwarz criterion, and Hannan-Quinn criterion, and at which the model is not affected by serial correlation.

Table 6: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: UNEMP INFR PCRGDP GFCF

TGE

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 09/02/25 Time: 20:59

Sample: 1981 2023

Included observations: 40

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1219.543	NA	2.68e+20	61.22717	61.43828	61.30350
1	-1026.887	327.5162*	6.20e+16*	52.84434	54.11100	53.30232
2	-1002.486	35.38137	6.80e+16	52.87429*	55.19650*	53.71393*
3	-986.6281	19.02929	1.26e+17	53.33140	56.70916	54.55269

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Computed from E-view

From table 6, the optimal lag length for the error correction model (ECM) is lag 2 based on the Akaike information criterion.

4.5 Estimated Short-Run (Error Correction Model) Result

The parsimonious short-run (error correction model) result is presented in table 7.

Table 7: Estimated Error Correction Model (ECM) Result

Dependent Variable: D(UNEMP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 09/03/25 Time: 06:27

Sample (adjusted): 1984 2023

Included observations: 40 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.503017	0.984631	-1.526477	0.1370
D(UNEMP(-1))	0.450288	0.194113	2.319724	0.0271
D(UNEMP(-2))	0.317054	0.178961	1.771634	0.0863
D(INFR(-1))	0.545460	0.133637	4.081671	0.0002
DLOG(PCRGDP(-2))	7.499095	3.056166	2.453759	0.0186
DLOG(GFCF(-1))	-8.566816	4.052805	-2.113799	0.0427
DLOG(GFCF(-2))	-7.905095	3.721064	-2.124418	0.0417
DLOG(TGE)	5.084208	3.377308	1.505403	0.1423
ECM(-1)	-0.698252	0.217029	-3.217322	0.0027
R-squared	0.672642	Mean dependent var		0.507500
Adjusted R-squared	0.536549	S.D. dependent var		4.785319
S.E. of regression	3.897761	Akaike info criterion		5.753789
Sum squared resid	470.9688	Schwarz criterion		6.133787
Log likelihood	-106.0758	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.891185
F-statistic	3.472947	Durbin-Watson stat		2.100615
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005699			

Source: Computed from E-view

From the ECM result in table 7, the error correct term (ECM(-)) turned up with a correct negative coefficient and it is also significant at the 0.05 level of significance. The coefficient of the ECM(-1) variable is -0.698252. This means that any disequilibrium in the short-run is reconciled to the long-run (equilibrium) trend of the model with a speed of adjustment of about 69 percent within a year in the current period.

4.6 Post-Estimation Tests

The classical linear regression model (CLRM) is based on certain assumptions. These assumptions need to be satisfied for the estimated regression result to be valid. The results and decisions for the tests of these assumptions are summarized in table 8 and figures 1 and 2.

Table 8: Post Estimation Test Results

Test	Value	Prob.	Decision
Linearity (Ramsey-RESET Test)			
t-Statistic	1.718467	0.0960	Accept H ₀ : (Model is Correctly specified)
F-Statistic	2.953129	0.0960	
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correction LM Test			Accept H ₀ : (No Serial correlation)
F – Statistic	2.161900	0.1333	
Heteroscedasticity Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey)Test			Accept H ₀ : (Model is Homoscedastic as a result of constant variance)
F - Statistic	1.646276	0.1521	

Normality (Jacque-Bera) Test			Accept Ho: (Data normally distributed)
F-Statistic	0.767651	0.681250	

Source: Computed from E – View

Figure 1: Cumulative Sum Test for stability

Source: From E-view

Figure 2: Cumulative Sum Squares Test for Stability

Source: From E-view

For each of the post estimation test results in table 8, the null hypothesis is accepted since the probability value is greater than 0.05. For the stability tests in figures 1 and 2, since the plots lie within the 5 percent critical bounds, the estimated model is considered stable.

4.7 Discussion of Findings

4.7.1 Long-Run Regression Result

From the estimated long-run coefficients in table 5, the coefficient of inflation rate turned up with a wrong positive sign based on the apriori theoretical reasoning. Thus, an increase in the rate of inflation will bring about an increase in the rate of unemployment. Inflation rate is however not significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, one percent increase in the rate of inflation is associated with an average increase of

0.104295 percent in unemployment rate. The implication of the positive sign of the coefficient of inflation rate is that the Phillips curve does not exist in Nigeria. Rather, what exists is stagflation – a simultaneous increase in both inflation and unemployment. This collaborates the findings of Orji et al (2015), Odo et al (2017), Irewole (2019), Nzidee and Uzorka (2019), Umar et al (2021), Anoke et al (2021), Okoebor et al (2022), and Onwuemeka et al (2024). The findings is however in disagreement with the findings of Babatunde et al (2020), Daniel et al (2021), Okeowo (2023), Nwikipo (2023), and Aliyu et al (2024) which established negative relationship between unemployment and inflation in Nigeria.

Further, per capital real GDP and gross fixed capital formation have significant negative impact on unemployment. This implies that an increase in each of per capita real GDP and gross fixed capital formation will bring about a reduction in the rate of unemployment. Thus, ₦1 million increase in per capital real GDP is associated with an average reduction of 0.110474 percent in unemployment rate while ₦1 billion increase in gross fixed capital formation is associated with an average decrease of 0.003606 percent in unemployment rate. Total government expenditure has insignificant negative impact on unemployment rate. The implication is that an increase in total government expenditure will bring about a decrease in unemployment. Thus, ₦1 billion increase in total government expenditure is associated with an average reduction of 0.001416 percent in unemployment rate.

4.7.2 Short-run Regression Result

From the estimated short-run (ECM) result in table 7, unemployment rate lagged by one period has significant positive impact on unemployment rate in the current period while unemployment lagged by two periods has insignificant positive impact on unemployment rate in the current period. The implication is that past levels of unemployment aggravates unemployment in the current period. Inflation rate lagged by one period has significant positive impact on unemployment rate. Similarly, per capita real GDP lagged by two periods has significant positive impact on the current rate of unemployment. On the other hand, lagged values of gross fixed capital formation in periods one and two have significant negative impact on current rate of unemployment while total government expenditure has significant positive impact on unemployment rate.

The estimated short-run regression result also indicated that the error correction term turned up with the right negative coefficient and it is also significant at the 0.05 level of significance. The coefficient of the error correction term is -0.698252. This implies that any disequilibrium in the short-run is reconciled to the long-run (equilibrium) trend of the model with a speed of adjustment of about 69 percent within one year in the current period.

Further, the estimated short-run regression result showed that the coefficient of multiple determination (R-squared) is 0.672642. This means that the explanatory variables jointly explain about 67 percent of the total variations in the level of unemployment in Nigeria. The remaining 23 percent is attributed to variables covered by the stochastic variable. The adjusted R-squared is 0.536549. The implication is that if additional explanatory variables are introduced to the model, the R-squared will reduce to 0.536549 due to the loss of degree of freedom. In other words, as more explanatory variables are added to the model, all the explanatory variables together would account for about 53 percent of the total variations in the dependent variable. The estimated F-Statistic is 3.472947 with an estimated probability value of 0.005699. Thus, since the estimated probability value of the F-statistic is less than 0.05, the implication is that the overall estimated regression model is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Finally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.100615 is greater than 2. This means that the estimated short-run result is not affected by the problem of serial correlation of the residuals.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between inflation and unemployment as a way of testing the validity of the Phillips curve in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the Phillips curve does not exist in Nigeria. Rather, what exists in Nigeria is stagflation – a situation where high inflation rate exists concurrently with high unemployment rate.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following policy measures are recommended.

- i. Since the study established positive relationship between unemployment and inflation (i.e., stagflation) in Nigeria, there is the need to implement policies that will curb both inflation and unemployment concurrently. Specifically, the government should exhibit fiscal prudence to reduce non-essential spending and to improve public service delivery. There is also the need for monetary policy measures to discourage unproductive borrowing and spending and to promote savings and investments through the interest rate mechanism.
- ii. The government should introduce supply-side economic reforms such as investment in infrastructure to boost local productive capacity; structural changes through diversification so as to reduce shocks to the economy from oil price volatility; etc. These measures will help to increase economic productivity, lower costs of production, stabilize prices, and create a conducive macroeconomic environment for sustainable economic growth and job creation.
- iii. There is the need to improve the country's macroeconomic environment and ease of doing business so as to attract the inflow of foreign capital to augment domestic capital so as to enhance the productive capacity of the economy to produce more goods and services, and to create additional jobs.

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